

TRANS-REGIONALISM, REGIONALISM, AND REALISM ARE WHAT EXPLAIN INDIA-PAKISTAN RELATIONS UNDER THE SHANGHAI COOPERATION ORGANIZATION

Dr. Inamullah Jan^{*1}, Hameed Ullah Khan²

^{*1}IRI Postdoctoral Fellow at Islamic Research Institute, International Islamic University & Lecture at Department of Politics & IR International Islamic University Islamabad

²Lecturer in Political Science, Department of Political Science, University Swabi, (Pakistan)

¹inamullah.jan@iiu.edu.pk, ²hameed.phdps57@iiu.edu.pk

²<http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1515-9236>

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Inamullah Jan

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ABSTRACT

Regionalism, along with realism and trans-regionalism, has largely shaped relations between India and Pakistan in the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). This paper will therefore seek to analyze how the three theoretical perspectives have influenced the interaction between India and Pakistan within the context of the SCO. India and Pakistan joined the SCO as member states from the South Asian region, and as a trans-regional organization, the SCO has given both countries the chance to engage in multilateral diplomacy and discussions. This has enabled both countries to be in a position to deal with common interests and factor areas of interaction apart from the prevalent tension. It has also compelled India and Pakistan to play the regional cards, though they cooperate and compete with each other in the organization to define their regional power in the SCO. Realism, a tradition of inter-state interests and power balance, has played a significant role in the India-Pakistan relationship within the SCO. Both countries have utilized the SCO to further their strategic and security interests, thus showing cooperation along with potential competition.

Keywords: India-Pakistan relations, Shanghai Cooperation Organization, trans-regionalism, regionalism, realism, regional security, conflict resolution.

INTRODUCTION

These two states have had conflicting relations since the partition of British India into India and Pakistan in 1947. The split caused mass displacement, and sectarian violence, and the Kashmir dispute became a central issue. At the time of partition the region, inhabited by Muslims, ruled by a Hindu Maharaja who firstly required independence but later accepted India military help against the Pakistani tribesmen which led to the first Indo-Pakistani war of 1947 to 1949 (Wolpert, 1984).

The conflict ended with the formation of Line of Control. India and Pakistan fought four wars over the territory of Kashmir: in 1965, 1970-71, 1999. The 1971 war led to the formation of Bangladesh, which was previously the south-eastern part of Pakistan. The conflict also has a nuclear angle, with India conducting nuclear tests in 1974 and Pakistan in 1998. Other disputes are water sharing, state treatment of religious minorities, and so on; terrorism is also a potential area of conflict, with both blame each other supporting

insurgents Talbot, 2009). In spite of diplomatic works, such as the Simla Agreement of 1972 and the Lahore Declaration of 1999, relations remain tense (Jalal, 1994).

The SCO is a regional organization formed in April 1996 to coordinate the fight against terrorism and maintain security on the Eurasian continent. Firstly known as the “Shanghai Five” it became the SCO after Uzbekistan joined 2001. The organization aims to improve multilateral diplomacy in spheres security and defense, foreign affairs and trade, culture, and banking. The organization has shifted from solving border problems to expanding cooperation in the political, economic, cultural, educational spheres (Khan et al., 2023). Member’s states collaborate on projects in energy, hydrocarbons, and the management of water resources. The SCO also works to fight terrorism and ensure regional stability, directed by “Shanghai Spirit” principles, which include trust, mutual benefit, equality, consultation, recognition of divergent civilizations, and development for all (Khan et al., 2023). With this mechanism, the SCO has the potential for greater impact and results in the upcoming.

All three theoretical paradigms form how India’s and Pakistan’s SCO membership affects their bilateral relations. Realism, much attention is paid to national interests and power relations; (Mearsheimer, 2003); thought that the SCO could lead to the confrontation between the two states. However, as the SCO emphasizes regional security, it also makes it possible to forge counterterrorism and border security that may enhance regionalism above the historical animosity. Trans-regionalism could be promoted by joint SCO actions with other regional organizations (Acharya, 2002), encouraging dialogues beyond security, such as trade and culture. However, the unresolved Kashmir dispute remains a key challenge, and it is doubtful whether the SCO can facilitate larger cooperation or remain incomplete by realist rivalry.

Review of Related Literature

India and Pakistan enmity mainly due to Kashmir issue. Despite efforts like the Shimla Agreement and the Lahore Declaration; these attempts have failed due to political factors and

role of armed forces in Pakistan (Parveen, 2023). The 1947 partition fostered nationalism on both sides, which made them unable to forget the past and work for peace (Hussain, 2019). The media in both countries has played a role fuelling the tension by shaping public opinion. Pakistan also faces regional challenges with India powering threatened by China, a close ally of Pakistan (Sugunakararaju and Akhtar, 2015). The United States has been attempting to mediate between the two, but often its actions are apparent as preferring one side. With both countries owning nuclear weapons, tensions are increased (Hussain, 2019). Moreover, shared allegation of backing terrorist groups, promote hinders cooperation in fighting terrorism.

Realism is a dominant paradigm justifying the India-Pakistan relationships, watching the situation from a state-centered perspective. It implies that the states primarily to gain power and security in a self-help environment. Tensions between the two nations are best understood through concepts like security dilemmas, arms races, and power politics. Realists argue the conflict arises for the struggle for dominance in the area (Barry, 1998). In compare, liberalism’s highlights mutual dependence and institutions. Liberal theorists believe economic interdependence, democratization, and international organizations reduce conflict and promote peace. They also focus on economic cooperation, people-contact diplomacy, and the regional efforts, such as South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC), in reducing tension (Keohane and Nye 1973).

Constructivism argues that ideas, norms, and identities define the states’ interactions, challenging material realism and liberalism. It suggests that the India and Pakistan relations is influenced by adversaries’ identities and discourses not only by material factors. Constructivists believe that communication, trust, and Track II diplomacy can help transforming the hostile relations between the two states (Wendt, 1992).

Post-colonialism offers a critical view of India-Pakistan relations, emphasizing the colonial impact on their identities, narratives, and political cultures. It claims that the partition

and the creation of Pakistan formed the leading dynamics in both states. Post-colonial theorists consider this historical perspective vital to considerate the resolution of the conflict and possible solutions (Spivak, 2012).

Trans-regionalism calls for the interaction across different regions, fostering inter-boundary relationships and challenging the idea that countries should concentrate on a particular region (Nye Jr, 2003). The SCO originally a regional security organization in Central Asia now extended to the members of South Asia and other regions. The founding principles—mutual trust, non-interference, and respect for the sovereignty—correlate with the trans-regionalist approach. The organization counters security issues, like terrorism, separatism, and extremism, using a joint approach that covers many countries (Giustozzi and Matveeva, 2008). Economically, it connects Central and South Asia through initiatives like the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) to enhancing economic cooperation. Politically, the SCO poses competition to the Western-led globalization and balances hegemony in the Central Asian region, indicates the shift towards a multipolar world in which trans-regional organizations play a better role in global governance (Haffiza, 2023). Regionalism, a post-World War II concept, deals with collective economic and political unity amongst geographical regions (Nye Jr, 2003). In South Asia, SAARC was established in 1985 to foster regional integration but has been hampered by a lack of trust, especially between India and Pakistan. Regionalism in South Asia is assessed through "region-ness," surrounding geographic unit, social structures, transnational cooperation, regional communities, and "region state" (Ahmed and Bhatnagar, 2008). In Central Asia Uzbekistan leadership change in 2016, stressed regional integration, people and goods exchanges, border collaboration, and approaching common regional security issues (Choi, 2023). Organizations like the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) have supported regional integration over competition and internal politics have influenced progress (Smith, 1996).

Theoretical Frameworks

Trans-regionalism raises collaboration and integration beyond particular regions, connecting countries from different regions and creating new relationships and institutions (Middell, 2018). It contains bilateral cooperation countries from different regions, and multilateral cooperation among regional organizations (Hamanaka, 2023). Examples are the Asia-Europe Meeting (ASEM), and the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) (Rüland, 2011). Projects like China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) represent trans-regionalism by enhancing economic cooperation and infrastructure development across Asia, Africa, and Europe. Trans-regionalism addresses globalization and global challenges, the furthering and development of economic integration, fosters economic integration and enlarges political and security cooperation (Sufiyanova and Muslimova, 2021). However, trans-regional integrated projects require member countries to reconcile differences and cooperate to common objectives (Kim, 2003).

Regionalism is the integration activities in the region over share goals, interests, and aims (Mansfield and Solingen, 2010). It includes founding political, economic, and social institutions based on specific geographical location (Panagariya, 1999). Examples include the European Union (EU), the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA), and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). The rise of regionalism includes globalization and the need to address global challenges and opportunities at a regional level for political, economic, and security cooperation (Fawcett, 2004).

Realism is a theoretical approach in international relations emphasizing state power, national interest, and survival in an anarchic international system. Realist's perspective, states are rational and self-serving actors focused on their existence and welfare in the absence of a central authority (Mearsheimer, 2003). For realists the state, its population, political regime, borders, cultures, and economy are of greatest importance (Wohlforth, 2011). They are suspicious about systemic change because inherent impediments in human nature, political systems, state

anarchy (Wild, 1947). Since Second World War, realism has become the leading approach to international relations theory, provides the best interpretation of states' behavior and course of action to tackle international anarchy. However, within the SCO, power competition based on national interests could delay cooperation in favor of individual security interests.

Analyzing Indo-Pak within the SCO framework essential refer to paradigms like trans-regionalism, regionalism, and realism. Trans-regionalism is valid as the SCO unites countries from different regions, such as India and Pakistan, to meet common challenges and enhance economic cooperation. Regionalism, on the other hand, is based on cooperation between countries in the same geographic region; the SCO enhances interactions between its members, despite the longstanding animosity between India and Pakistan. Realism, which focusses on nation-states' interests, power, and security challenges, is also suitable for understanding their interactions within the SCO. Both countries hold opposing regional ideologies and strategies and their participation is based on self-interests and security threats. Nevertheless, the SCO provides a platform for discussing and cooperating on issues as counter-terrorism and economic cooperation.

India and Pakistan under the Auspices of the SCO

The SCO, founded in 2001, composed of China, Russia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan. Historically, the main priorities were countering terrorism, separatism, and extremism in Central Asia (Khan and Mahmood, 2023). The SCO Charter, adopted at the St. Petersburg Summit in June 2002, defined its goals and principles, structure, and main spheres of activities. Over time, the organization expanded to include India, Pakistan, and Iran as regular members, with Afghanistan, Belarus, and Mongolia as dialogue partners. Today, the SCO turned its attention to economic cooperation through the SCO Business Council and SCO Interbank Consortium, following investment projects sponsored by the member governments (Dexue, 2021).

SCO is an international organization, mainly dealing with security and fighting against terrorism. Its Charter shapes objectives such as fighting terrorism, separatism, extremism, drug trafficking, transnational crime, and international information security (Aris, 2013). The Regional Anti-Terrorist Structure (RATS) of SCO deals intelligence sharing, military exercises, economic interaction, and cultural and people-to-people relations (Khan et al., 2023). However, different interests and objectives among members, especially India and Pakistan or China and India, pose challenges to enhancing regional security and stability (Kumar, 2024).

The admission of both India and Pakistan into the SCO has strategic consequences for the region. The SCO currently has 3 billion people and a quarter of the global economy (Mughal, 2021; Sethi, 2017). SCO benefits from their memberships through regional integration, counterterrorism measures, and economic cooperation. Their role supports its goal of fostering peace, stability, and cooperation, while provides a forum for communication, dispute settlement, and regional security integration (Kizilay, 2023).

Both India and Pakistan joined the Organization in 2017, looking forward to the economic integration and cooperation. The SCO led by major countries like China and Russia, aims to create a stable region through cooperation. India and Pakistan membership has empowered bilateral trade in their own currencies, agricultural cooperation, and the development of micro, small, and medium enterprises. The SCO provides a format to restore and continue bilateral trade in sphere of agriculture, textiles, and energy to reduce dependence on the Western financial system (Raza, 2023; ur Rehman, 2014). The SCO can contribute to the development of transport corridors to enhance connectivity such as the Turkmenistan - Afghanistan - Pakistan - India (TAPI) Gas Pipeline ensuring energy security and interdependence (Khan, 2021). Enhancing connectivity through transport could increase trade and economic relations. However, there is concern about the extent of security risks including cross-border terrorism and instability in Afghanistan (Raza, 2023; ur Rehman, 2014).

These concerns can be tackled collectively within the SCO framework, adopting an environment conducive to economic cooperation. The recent meeting of the SCO's foreign ministers in India with Pakistan's Bilawal Bhutto Zardari also shows a possibility of dialogue and cooperation in economic relations under the SCO (Rauf, 2019).

Competition and cooperation have risen since India and Pakistan became members of the SCO. The SCO provides a forum to discuss regional issues without focusing on bilateral conflict. Its principles of non-interference and mutual respect offer for dealing with common problems such as terrorism and economic growth. Recent meeting of the SCO and thus seem willing to interact (Adil, 2023). The SCO's objectives of regional stability are important for both countries due to threats such as terrorism or instability in Afghanistan (Rauf & Tariq, 2024). Dialogue within the SCO framework could minimize the impact of bilateral controversies on regional stability. Future meetings offer exposure to more engagement and pave the way for specific inter-state talks (Raza, 2023). Experts supposed the SCO could result in a stabilization of relations and increase cooperation in economic sector.

India and Pakistan have cooperated in countering terrorism within the SCO's RATS, despite the bilateral clash. Both nations faced terrorism threats that endangered regional insecurity. Indian Foreign Minister S. Jaishankar, highlighted the essence of this cooperation, while Pakistani Foreign Minister Bilawal Bhutto Zardari asserted Pakistan's commitment to being an active participant in SCO counter-terrorism measures. The two countries finalized a plan in August to conduct joint military drills under the SCO in the Ural Mountains of Russia. Kamal Dawar, the founder of the India's defense intelligence agency, stressed that the role of Pakistan should not be only ceremonial: 'It will be useful to restore communication (Peri, and Bhattacharjee, 2022).

Key Issues in India-Pakistan Relations ***Security Dilemma***

The term security dilemma is widely used in international relations theories. It describes a scenario where two or more states strive to increase their own security while simultaneously reducing that of others. After the division of India, the ongoing competition and shifting power dynamics between India and Pakistan can be described as a security dilemma. In the South Asian system, both countries fear subjugation, domination, or incorporation by the other. This fear drives each to enhance its capabilities and power to ensure national security, even if it worsens insecurity for the other.

India and Pakistan view each other as security threats, a perception rooted in the partition of British India, the Kashmir dispute, and several wars. This has fueled an arms race, with both countries striving to enhance their military capabilities. India perceives Pakistan as a hostile state that sponsors terrorism, particularly in Kashmir, and views Islamabad's nuclear capability as a significant threat (Panjra, 2018). To some extent, India's military expansion is a response to the perceived Pakistani threat. On the other hand, Pakistan sees India as a hegemonic power seeking regional dominance. Islamabad's development of nuclear power is largely a response to India's conventional military superiority, a justification the Pakistani government heavily relies on as India continues to bolster its military strength (Ali and Bukhari, 2022).

The conflict between India and Pakistan remains a persistent source of tension and an ongoing arms race. Under the Modi government, India has increasingly positioned itself as a global power, aspiring to lead the South Asian subcontinent and play a significant role on the world stage. Modi's vision of making the 21st century "the century of India" has driven efforts to enhance India's military capabilities. As of 2019, India ranks as the fourth most powerful military globally, while Pakistan ranks seventeenth, according to global firepower indices (You, 2019). The following table shows the relative power of their armed forces:

Table.1 military might comparison between India and Pakistan in 2019

Subjects	India	Pakistan
Total Military Personnel	1,400,000	654,000
Defense Budget (USD)	74 billions \$	10.4 billions \$
Total Aircraft	2,263	1,531
Total Tank and Armor	4,616	3,742
Total Naval Assets	267	96
Helicopters	729	400
Railway Coverage (km)	63974	7791

Sources:

[https://armedforces.eu/compare/country/India vs Pakistan](https://armedforces.eu/compare/country/India_vs_Pakistan)

The numbers in the table clearly indicate India's superior firepower over Pakistan. The Modi government has prioritized enhancing India's military capabilities, with the defense ministry consistently receiving a larger share of the budget compared to other ministries. This has heightened Pakistan's concerns about India's ambitions to maintain regional hegemony in South Asia and the growing disparity in their military strength.

Effects of Nuclear Capabilities on Stabilization of a Region

Both India and Pakistan have nuclear weapons, and they have destabilized the peace in South Asia. They have sufficient quantity and quality of nuclear weapons to prevent full-scale war; however, constructing more weapons, power, new technology, and a variety of war strategies in the region is making it insecure. India and Pakistan face challenges with nuclear doctrines, proportionality, and escalation management (Levesques, 2024). India appears to favor counterforce targeting, pressuring Pakistan to enhance its nuclear capabilities (Ashraf, 2023). Meanwhile, Pakistan's 'full spectrum deterrence' doctrine allows nuclear response to low-scale conventional conflicts (Das, 2023).

With a focus on below-nuclear threshold strategies, India and Pakistan are advancing technologies against each other's defenses (Ashraf, 2023). India is developing counterforce nuclear assets, including tactical delivery systems, MIRV, and BMD. Pakistan has introduced short-range tactical nuclear weapons like the Hatf IX Nasr and nuclear-capable cruise missiles (Das, 2023). The internal political setting in both countries may

influence the ability to command and control nuclear weapons. In Pakistan, political instability, such as Pakistan's conflict between Imran Khan and the military, may impact nuclear command and control. The Lahore Declaration and the Agreement on Pre-notification of Ballistic Missile Tests show that India and Pakistan's nuclear confidence-building measures remain underutilized. Strengthening trust requires broader NCBMs and genuine attention to public concerns (Saadia, 2014).

Economic Cooperation and Competition

India and Pakistan have had tense relations, especially in trade. After India changed Jammu and Kashmir's status in August 2019, Pakistan halted imports, move critics saw as economically harmful to both nations. Despite being major South Asian economies, political tensions limit trade (Raza, 2023). However, recent reports indicate significant growth in bilateral trade. In the first eight months of this year, India's exports to Pakistan rose 72% to \$205 million, while Pakistan's exports to India reached \$17.6 million. Most of India's imports from Pakistan arrived via tankers (*"GT voice: Will India"*, 2022).

At the 2021 SCO meeting, India and Pakistan expressed willingness to cooperate. Indian PM Narendra Modi discussed regional integration, stating India could work with Pakistan under favorable conditions. Pakistani PM Imran Khan also emphasized the need for regional cooperation, highlighting trade and connectivity as key SCO goals. He recently stated that Pakistan seeks trade ties with all SCO members, including India, for mutual benefit (*"SCO Summit 2021"*, 2021).

Challenges Posed by Historical Animosities

India and Pakistan have always had differences, and this makes it difficult for them to cooperate on economic issues. The Kashmir dispute, with both nations seeking full control, has led to wars and military confrontations, fueling distrust and hindering economic integration.

Official statements from both nations confirm ongoing tensions. At a recent SCO meeting, Indian PM Narendra Modi stated, 'Negotiations and terrorism cannot go hand in hand,' referring to Pakistan's alleged support for terrorism. Meanwhile, Pakistan's Foreign Minister Zardari emphasized the need for internal stability before improving ties with India (Ahad, 2023).

External Influences

The involvement of superpowers like China, Russia, and the United States heavily influences India and Pakistan's relations, often complicating efforts for cooperation between the two nations. As a strategic partner, China significantly influences South Asian geopolitics. The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) has strengthened economic ties and provided China with vital access to the Arabian Sea. India views this partnership as a threat to its regional dominance. While the SCO promotes Chinese relations with both India and Pakistan, it also creates a dilemma for India, particularly in its conflict with Pakistan (Kizilay, 2023; Turner, 2005).

Russia plays a key role in the SCO, maintaining neutrality between India and Pakistan while encouraging communication. However, its growing defense and energy cooperation with Pakistan has caused discomfort for India. While Russia's mediation within the SCO presents an opportunity, it also gives the impression of bias toward Pakistan, influencing India's strategy. Historically, Russia has been an ally of India but has provided arms and support to Pakistan, especially when the U.S. accused Pakistan of supporting terrorism. Russia's primary goal is to challenge the U.S. in the region, rather than resolve India-Pakistan issues (Ahmed et al., 2019; Kupriyanov, 2020; You, 2019).

The U.S. has developed strong ties with India, particularly in defense and trade, while its

relationship with Pakistan remains complex due to counter-terrorism concerns. Although the U.S. seeks to promote communication between India and Pakistan, its actions sometimes fuel further hostility ("U.S. Encourages India and Pakistan", 2024). U.S. involvement in South Asia, especially post-Afghanistan War, shifted regional power dynamics, intensifying rivalry between India and Pakistan. While the U.S. previously supported Pakistan in fighting terrorism, this assistance was often self-serving. Under Trump, the U.S. bolstered its alliance with India, deepening the power gap between New Delhi and Islamabad. U.S. actions are driven by strategic interests, which can conflict with the SCO's vision for regional stability (Putz, 2023).

Trans-Regionalism in the SCO

Trans-regionalism refers to cooperation and connectivity between different global regions. Trans-regional organizations are broader than regional ones like the EU or ASEAN, as they cover larger geographical areas and involve more countries.

Trans-regionalism is implemented through frameworks that bridge regional boundaries. The SCO brings together Central Asia (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan), South Asia (India, Pakistan), East Asia (China, Russia), and North Asia (Russia), fostering cooperation, consultations, and exchanges on various issues. This diverse membership makes the SCO a unique platform for trans-regional cooperation.

The prospects for trans-regionalism within the SCO are still evolving, but it offers hope for improving India-Pakistan relations. By fostering collaboration across regional boundaries, the SCO engages India, Pakistan, and Kazakhstan on issues beyond immediate security threats. This could enable India and Pakistan to collaborate on SCO projects with other regional organizations like SAARC, potentially leading to dialogue on trade or cultural exchange and progress on bilateral matters (Raza, 2023). Trans-regional integration ultimately depends on both countries' willingness to move beyond a competitive, realist framework.

Mechanisms of Trans-Regional Cooperation in the SCO

Membership and Structure: Founded in 2001, the SCO expanded from six to nine member countries by 2023, covering much of the European continent and a significant global population. Its members include China, India, Pakistan, Russia, and several Central Asian nations, all working together to address regional issues. The SCO's governance includes the Heads of State Council, which meets annually to set priorities, and the RATS, focused on security within the member countries (Azizi, 2024; Huaxia, 2024).

Security Cooperation:

Security is a key focus of the SCO, particularly in combating terrorism, separatism, and extremism. The creation of RATS in 2004 highlights the SCO's commitment to cooperative security, encouraging military training, intelligence sharing, and joint anti-terrorism operations. This collaboration promotes regional stability and reduces the potential for rivalry (Giustozzi and Matveeva, 2008). At the SCO Foreign Ministers' Meeting, Indian Foreign Minister S. Jaishankar emphasized the importance of collective action against terrorism. Meanwhile, Pakistani Foreign Minister Bilawal Bhutto Zardari highlighted Pakistan's commitment to the SCO Charter, despite ongoing bilateral conflicts (Mehrotra and Gupta, 2023).

Economic Connectivity:

The SCO also prioritizes economic integration, focusing on trade and investment among member countries. Socioeconomic cooperation is another key aspect, with the SCO Business Council and the SCO Interbank Consortium playing crucial roles. Additionally, the SCO supports the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which enhances infrastructure and links member states to boost their economies. Recently, Chinese President Xi Jinping highlighted the SCO's vision of connectivity and cooperation, stating, 'The SCO is today a unifying voice for connectivity and cooperation, and for openness and inclusiveness,' underscoring its ability to address common challenges (Azizi, 2024).

Cultural and Educational Exchange:

The SCO values cultural and educational cooperation as a way to enhance understanding among member states. Initiatives like SCO University promote academic collaboration and professional exchange, fostering positive attitudes and long-term partnerships for future generations (Huaxia, 2024).

Trans-regionalism within the SCO faces several challenges. The diverse interests of its broad membership make consensus difficult, as countries have varying preferences. Major powers like Russia and China can dominate decision-making, often sidelining smaller members' concerns. International disputes, such as the India-Pakistan conflict, further hinder the organization's effectiveness. Additionally, conflicting interests arise as New Delhi opposes China, while Islamabad seeks to strengthen its position within the SCO (Waggy and Hassan, 2023).

The SCO offers numerous opportunities, acting as a regional integration platform that promotes economic growth through trade and investment. It also enhances security cooperation, helping member countries combat terrorism, drug trafficking, and organized crime (Ahmed et al., 2019). Trans-regional initiatives like the BRI could shift regional dynamics and impact the strategies of both India and Pakistan. Additionally, cultural events within the SCO foster social ties, contributing to harmony among member states. The SCO's involvement can positively influence India-Pakistan relations, encouraging both to tackle shared regional challenges, such as extremism and terrorism in Afghanistan (Rauf, 2019).

Regionalism and the SCO's Role in South Asia

Regionalism plays a significant role in India-Pakistan relations within the SCO, given their tense history. While not a South Asian organization, the SCO provides a platform for cooperation and integration between the two nations, promoting collaboration on common security and economic issues (Rauf, 2019). Through the SCO, India and Pakistan can address mutual concerns within a regional context. While the SCO encourages regionalism, it could help build trust and reduce conflict. However, challenges persist,

notably the unresolved Kashmir issue (Akhtar and Kiran, 2018), with both countries often viewing their SCO activities through a realist lens, focusing on self-interest and competition rather than genuine regional integration (Mearsheimer, 2003).

The SCO has been involved in various initiatives aimed at promoting stability and cooperation in the region. One such initiative is RATS, which facilitates intelligence-sharing for counter-terrorism efforts, even amid strained India-Pakistan relations. The SCO also emphasizes economic cooperation, like the SCO Development Strategy 2025, which aims to boost trade and communication among member states. Additionally, the organization fosters cultural and people-to-people exchanges to improve understanding. Despite challenges, the SCO remains an important platform for dialogue, helping improve relations between members, such as India and Pakistan, for greater unity and stability (Wani, 2023).

The SCO has supported regional initiatives involving India and Pakistan, though their relations remain largely unaffected. Examples include the 2018 SCO Summit in Qingdao, where Indian PM Narendra Modi and Pakistani President Mamnoon Hussain showed willingness to engage despite tensions, and the 2019 joint counter-terrorism exercise in Russia under the SCO framework. The November 2019 inauguration of the Kartarpur Corridor also aligns with the SCO's focus on increasing connectivity. However, efforts are hindered by trust deficits, terrorism allegations, and political tensions that limit economic interactions and trade (Chawla, 2023; Wani, 2023). The participation of Pakistan's Foreign Minister Bilawal Bhutto Zardari at the May 2023 SCO meeting could signal a shift toward diplomatic engagement, suggesting that for regional integration to succeed in South Asia, overcoming hostility is crucial.

Realism and Power Politics in the SCO

The SCO largely operates within a realist framework, as seen in the India-Pakistan confrontation. Realist theory suggests that states act in self-interest, often creating a security dilemma where one state's efforts to enhance security may negatively affect others. This dynamic is evident in the SCO, where

India and Pakistan are both complementary and competitive. India uses the SCO to counter China's growing influence, while Pakistan seeks to strengthen ties with China and Russia for security against India. According to realism, both countries are driven by self-interest in joining the SCO to advance their positions and secure regional influence, not to foster harmony. Historical tensions, especially over Kashmir, exacerbate the security dilemma, leading to reciprocal actions. Their strategic interests align with broader global partnerships: India with the U.S., and Pakistan with China, both aiming to balance the other's influence. These tensions are evident at the official level, with India accusing Pakistan of supporting terrorism and Pakistan accusing India of interference (Joobani, 2013; Mearsheimer, 2023; Preda, 2022). The realist approach also highlights the SCO's inability to resolve the India-Pakistan conflict, as the organization's principles of sovereign equality and non-intervention limit its capacity to address bilateral hostilities directly.

The SCO influences power dynamics in South Asia by bringing together key players, especially China and Russia, to counterbalance the U.S. presence in the region. Within the SCO, these nations coordinate policies and military actions, shaping regional power relations. A key aspect of this balance is China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which seeks to enhance economic connections in Asia, including South Asia, and strengthen ties between Central Asia, China, and Russia. This is concerning for India, which views the SCO's growing influence as a challenge to its traditional role as a regional power. SCO initiatives, such as counterterrorism and economic cooperation, can either heighten or ease tensions based on member states' actions. As both India and Pakistan seek to advance their interests, the SCO's power dynamics could impact regional stability and growth. While official statements do not explicitly address the balance of power, the SCO's goals of regional stability and development indirectly shape power relations in South Asia (Joobani, 2013; Preda, 2022).

The socio-political cooperation among SCO member countries and their relationships with external partners shape the organization's dynamics and effectiveness. While China and

Russia work to establish cooperation, their national interests, particularly in Central Asia, often lead to rivalry. The influence of global superpowers like the United States and the European Union also affects SCO relations. Formed partly in response to perceived Western dominance, the SCO provides its members a platform to assert their own priorities and counter external influence (Joobani, 2013; Preda, 2022).

To analyze India-Pakistan relations within the SCO, it's essential to apply trans-regionalism, regionalism, and realism together. Trans-regionalism highlights how global powers like China and Russia influence India-Pakistan relations within the SCO, extending beyond regional concerns. Regionalism is evident in the SCO's capacity for cooperation on issues like terrorism and economic development, even amid hostilities between some members. Realism, focused on power and security in a self-help system, best explains the security dilemma between India and Pakistan, driving competitive behaviors and hindering cooperation. Together, these perspectives offer insight into how global and regional factors shape India-Pakistan relations within the SCO.

Discussion and Conclusion

To understand India-Pakistan relations within the SCO, it's important to consider trans-regionalism, regionalism, and realism. Trans-regionalism shifts focus from immediate regional concerns, showing how China and Russia influence India-Pakistan relations within the SCO, affecting both global and regional dynamics. Regionalism looks at the potential for cooperation and integration in the region, with the SCO addressing issues like terrorism and economic crises despite bilateral disputes. Realism, with its emphasis on power and security in an anarchic system, explains why India and Pakistan struggle to cooperate within the SCO due to the security dilemma. Together, these frameworks highlight how global and regional factors shape India-Pakistan relations within the SCO.

Cooperation between India and Pakistan within the SCO hinges on their ability to set aside conflicting agendas and focus on shared objectives, such as combating terrorism and promoting economic integration. Ideally, the

SCO could foster Confidence-Building Measures (CBMs), with cooperation evolving gradually through joint projects. However, ongoing tensions could limit meaningful interaction, resulting in little progress and persistent hostility. In the worst case, escalating conflicts or new tensions could complicate SCO cooperation and undermine its stability goals in the region. The dynamics of these relations will be influenced by internal politics, the interests of China and Russia, economic ties, and security concerns. Despite these challenges, there remains potential for gradual progress if both sides leverage the SCO framework effectively.

To enhance India-Pakistan cooperation within the SCO, several strategies can be implemented: Regular high-level meetings within designated dialogue platforms can build trust and facilitate conflict resolution. Cooperation in areas like infrastructure development, counter-terrorism, and security could help reduce tensions. Initiatives like joint military exercises and exchange programs could also alleviate the security dilemma. Additionally, the SCO should adopt a proactive role in addressing conflicts, serving as a neutral mediator to encourage further dialogue and cooperation among its members.

By analyzing trans-regionalism, regionalism, and realism, this study explores the dynamics of the Indo-Pak relationship within the SCO context. It highlights that while the SCO offers opportunities for engagement, the volatile India-Pakistan relationship remains a significant challenge for collective initiatives. Trans-regionalism emphasizes the impact of extra-regional powers like China and Russia, while regionalism underscores the need for cooperation within the SCO to address issues like terrorism and economic challenges. Realism, on the other hand, explains the hostility and strategic motivations that impede cooperation—India seeks to counterbalance China's influence, while Pakistan aligns with China.

By applying trans-regionalism, regionalism, and realism, this research contributes to the fields of international relations and regional studies by analyzing India-Pakistan relations within the context of the SCO. It offers valuable insights into the interaction between global and

regional processes, bilateral conflicts, and cooperation, highlighting the SCO's influence on South Asian geopolitics. The study finds that historical enmity and geopolitical rivalry remain the primary barriers to regional cooperation, expanding our understanding of regional security and integration. This research builds on existing literature while deepening our comprehension of the dynamics within the SCO and the potential of regional organizations to shape international relations. To deepen our understanding of India-Pakistan relations within the SCO framework, future research should explore the following areas: First, investigating how SCO initiatives impact economic cooperation and counter-terrorism efforts could shed light on the effectiveness of regional collaboration. Additionally, comparing the strategies of SCO rivals in managing regional antagonisms may provide valuable insights for improving SCO cooperation. Future studies should also focus on the shifts in the bilateral relationship between India and Pakistan within the SCO context, while examining how global changes influence these relations. Moreover, exploring the perspectives of community activists and civil society in both countries could illuminate factors shaping governmental politics and reconciliation efforts. Lastly, future research should assess the role of the SCO in conflict resolution, the effects of domestic political transformations on SCO activities, and the role of non-governmental actors in promoting stability and integration within the region. Such investigations would contribute to developing strategies for fostering stability and cooperation in South Asia.

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